

Effect of Green Supply Chain Adoption on Supply Chain Performance in County Governments in Kenya

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Abstract

The main objective of the study was to determine the effect of green supply chain adoption on supply chain performance in county governments in Kenya. The research incorporated a descriptive survey design whereby the target population comprised of the Uasin Gishu County procurement, human resource, operations, stores and finance departments. The researcher adopted stratified random sampling and simple random sampling to select a sample size of 11 respondents. Questionnaires were the main data collection instruments that were incorporated in both closed-ended and open-ended questions. The collected data were checked for completeness and later coded into the SPSS software version 24, where descriptive and inferential statistics were determined. The findings show that environment management support has a positive and significant effect on supply chain performance, $\beta_3 = 0.505$, $p < 0.001$ and product re-usability has a negative and significant effect on supply chain performance, $\beta_4 = -0.150$, $p < 0.001$. There is a need to encourage recycling, there is also a need to address the structuring and restructuring of teams that are responsible for environmental improvements and putting in place a total quality environmental management plan and implementing it. Finally, proper enforcement mechanisms for product re-usability would enhance its effect on supply chain performance.

Keywords: *Environment Management Support, Supply Chain Performance, Product Re-Usability, County Governments*

Introduction

Global companies have highly invested in Green supply chain adoption for both long term purposes and short term purposes-meeting their customers' needs. Amongst the organizations that have a highly upheld Green supply chain include Samsung Group, LG Group, Panasonic Group and Toyota Company (Nabiswa, 2012). In other nations, greening laws and regulations have been passed and adequately implemented as laws of the land. According to Nabiswa (2012), Nevada acknowledges that in order to support the recycling ethic and to minimize environmental impacts, they will purchase recycled content and environmentally preferred products. The County of Nevada recognizes that its employees can make a difference in favor of environmental quality (Nabiswa, 2012). Therefore, they will purchase recycled content and environmentally preferable products unless such products do not perform satisfactorily and/or are unreasonably expensive (Nabiswa, 2012).

Organizations like Panasonic groups have their own Green supply chain Standards Ver. 6 (2012) that requests, the Panasonic suppliers establish an environmental management system and ensure comprehensive chemical substance management as well as expedite the reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, resource recycling and conservation of biodiversity. Being aware of the need to spread these initiatives across the Panasonic supply chain, suppliers have been encouraged to request upstream suppliers to reduce their environmental impact (Ondieki, 2012).

Non-governmental organizations like the United Nations Environmental Program (UNEP) and United Nations Office for Proposal Operations (UNOPS), the central procurement resource in the United Nations system, works towards including sustainability considerations in all its procurement. The UN Agencies strive to lead by example in their pursuit of the Green supply chain. This is through their many and varied UN activities. All UN organizations contribute to sustainable development in one way or another through economic development,

poverty alleviation, healthcare, peacebuilding, infrastructure support, or environmental protection. This is by ensuring the United Nations system embarks on a journey to move towards efficient resource management and climate neutrality (Kamonya & Iraki, 2013). The benefits to be realized out of this are better risk management, preparing the organization for a resource and carbon-constrained future, improving staff morale, and cutting costs UNOPS Delivering Sustainable Results Annual Report (2011).

Kenyan organizations practice the Green supply chain for various reasons ranging from energy conservation to lowering of their annual spending levels (Omariba & Iraki, 2013). Big organizations like Standard Chartered Bank Kenya Head Office in Nairobi adopted a new building, which is “environmentally friendly, energy-efficient and has large office areas which are very well laid out.” The building had been built to the Global Office Workplace Standards which are a clearly defined set of standards for all the Group’s new buildings across the world which is in the banks’ commitment to building a sustainable business over the long-term and is trusted worldwide for upholding high standards of corporate governance, social responsibility, environmental protection and employee diversity (Omariba & Iraki, 2013).

In light of increasing costs of waste management, environmental degradation, public health concerns, climate change, resource depletion, and persistent global poverty, the supply management profession is increasingly being called upon to contribute to broader organizational goals of sustainable development through the inclusion of social and environmental criteria within procurement processes (Srivastava, 2013). According to Kenya Solid Waste Management (2013), industrial wastes constitute about 23% of the total waste generated in the Nairobi city, only about 25% of the estimated 1,500 tons of solid waste generated daily get collected.

Environmental issues have not been fully addressed and that there are still challenges facing the effective implementation of the Green supply chain in Kenya. These challenges to GP include; resistance to technology advancement adoption, lack of organizational encouragement, lack of suppliers of sustainable assets, or services, lack of IT implementation, a perception that the process and outcomes are more costly or time consuming habit and the difficulty in changing procurement behavior, stakeholder involvement, principles, benchmarking and employee training among others (Lozano & Vallés, 2013). In 2010, for instance, a mere 14% of its agricultural supplies were sourced sustainably by its own definition. Now the share is 48% (UNEP, 2013).

Despite the important role Green supply chain plays in ensuring environmental performance and public health and safety, most of the studies on this subject had been conducted in developed countries, yet not much research had been conducted in Kenya leading to the insufficient empirical literature on Green supply chain (Stephen & Helen, 2011). Local studies so far done have focused on procurement in general (Otieno, 2004, Akech, 2005). the determinants of green public procurement adoption in Kenya with special focus to Kenya Pipeline Company by Ngugi (2014). The latest research was done by Catherine Gatari and Was (2014). It is against this background that this inquiry seeks to analyze factors affecting the implementation of the Green supply chain in the manufacturing sector in Kenya. Hence, the study strives to mitigate the gaps in research by analyzing the factors affecting the implementation of the Green supply chain in the manufacturing sector in Kenya. In this case, it is important for a study to be undertaken to specifically address the effect of the Green supply chain on supply chain performance in county governments in Kenya.

Theoretical Framework

The study was anchored on the Theory of Altruism. According to Schwartz' (2007), Altruism is a subset of pro-social behavior. The Theory of altruism suggests that pro-environmental behavior becomes more probable when an individual is aware of harmful consequences to others and when that person takes the detrimental effect of individualism in this context, (Hussein & Shalle, 2014) hypothesized that: Person with strong selfish and competitive orientation are less likely to act ecologically. People who have satisfied their personal needs are

more likely to act ecologically because they have more resources (time, money and energy) to care about bigger, less personal social and pro-environmental issues. Relating back to Schwartz ' work, the study of Stern (Gärling et al., 2003) examined the role that social altruism (concern of the welfare of others) and biospheric altruism (a concern for the non-human elements of the environment) play in influencing green behavior. In the same vein, (Mostafa, 2009) found that altruism has a significant positive effect on the intention to buy green products. Altruism provides a useful framework for understanding the psychological basis of consumer product choice in a global economy. The exact relationship between the variables of altruism and product choice has not been fully investigated. This paper reviews the literature and proposes a research framework to explore the effect of green supply chain adoption on supply chain performance.

Review of Literature

Environmental management support

This is the practice of developing green supply chain management as a strategic organizational imperative through commitment and support of the imperative from senior and mid-level managers. According to Kumar and Chandrakar (2012), top management support can affect new system initiatives success. Cross-functional efforts like supply chain performance are likely to benefit too. Like most other major environmental efforts, supply chain performance is a broad-based pervasive organizational endeavor with cross-functional programs. As such, it has the potential to benefit from top management support. General management support is a critical element of the adoption and implementation of innovations in an organization, especially environmental systems. Organizational innovations may remain stuck at the initial idea stage (Perotti *et al.*, 2012). In this case, it is not just top-level managers from whom support is needed; support from mid-level managers is also important to the successful implementation of environmental practices. Support from middle-management levels is important because environmental management is related to almost all departments in an organization, and cross-departmental cooperation is important to successful practices.

Product re-usability

Achieving a common understanding of what usability is can also be done by storytelling, by examining examples. Analyzing the potential consequences of usability is essential because the anticipated consequences of usability play an important role in the prioritization of usability (Hussein & Shalle, 2014). The effects of usability can be communicated by means of quantitative analysis, documenting for example product returns and customer satisfaction scores, but also through videos of user-product interaction or by having product developers and upper management experience their own products (Hussein & Shalle, 2014).

Product developers often describe usability as fuzzy and ungraspable (Shang et al., 2010). In order to reach a goal, you have to know what the goal is. In order to improve usability, you need a shared understanding of it (Roberts et al., 2008). The product can be used by specified users to achieve specified goals, with effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction, in a specified context of use.” Admittedly, due to its somewhat generic formulation, this definition does need to be made more specific to be useful (Mudgal *et al.*, 2009). Defining usability is one approach, but creating shared understanding might not require establishing a formal, explicit definition (Liu et al., 2012).

Product reusability is consisting of green packaging and green logistics. Packaging characteristics such as size, shape, and materials have an impact on distribution because of their effect on the transport characteristics of the product. Better packaging, along with rearranged loading patterns, can reduce materials usage, increase space utilization in the warehouse and in the trailer, and reduce the amount of handling required.

Reusability determines the overall profitability of a firm as it directly affects both the supply chain cost and the customer experience. Increased environmental awareness has led more companies to adopt sustainable, or green, distribution practices. These practices span from reducing the number of fossil fuels and greenhouse gases used in manufacture and distribution to increased emphasis on the environment during distribution. Khalifa and Shen (2008) define green supply chain management (GSCM) as the integration of environmental thinking into supply chain management, including product design, material sourcing and selection, manufacturing processes, delivery of the final product to the consumers, and end-of-life management of the product after its useful life.

Critique of existing literature

Kamonya and Iraki (2013) sought to establish the impact of Green supply chain adoption in small and medium enterprises in Nairobi. The study established that the majority of small and medium-size corporations in Nairobi have highly integrated the greening practices. In this case, the study came close to establishing the effect of green supply chain adoption but not on procurement adoption. Consequently, Ondieki (2012) sought to assess the level of Green supply chain awareness in the Kenyan state corporations. The study established that the level of Green supply chain amongst the Kenyan state corporations is significantly high. On the lower side, the study was only conducted in the Kenyan state corporations and not in the devolved system of government. Further, a study by Khisa (2011) sought to investigate Green supply chain adoption within the public sector in Kenya. In this case, the study established that following the government regulations in regard to the Green supply chain, most public corporations were practicing Green supply chain or were on the verge of integrating the greening practices.

Obiso (2011) study sought to investigate the green supply chain management in the devolved system of government. This study was close but was more focused on the issue of green supply chain management and not the effect of the Green supply chain on procurement management. Similarly, Omariba and Iraki (2013) investigated green supply chain management practices and supply chain performance in the mobile industry in Kenya. The study established that most of the firms in the mobile industry were practicing Green supply chain adoption. However, the study was only converged to the mobile industry and not the devolved system of government. The study by Eltayeb *et al.* (2013) came close to establishing the effect of the Green supply chain on supply chain performance in the Malaysian devolved system of government. However, the study was more inclined to the drivers of green purchasing and was conducted within the Malaysian devolved system of government.

Analysis of the past studies on the effect of green supply chain adoption on supply chain performance in county governments is crucial evidence that numerous scholars and researchers of the world have had undefined interests in this particular field of study. However, very few theoretical explanations developed by these researchers explore the key effects of green supply chain adoption on supply chain performance in county governments. It is to this regard that notable gaps are identified; eco- internal environmental management support and product re-usability. Therefore, this study was specifically narrowed down into these gaps with the aim of collecting relevant information to help develop a more theoretical explanation on the effects of green supply chain adoption on supply chain performance in county governments in Kenya.

Methodology

The study used a descriptive research design to help in indicating trends in attitudes and behaviors and enable generalization of the findings of the research study to be done. This study targets 1140 employees of Uasin Gishu County and cut across the following department's Procurement, Finance, Human Resource, Operations and Stores. The study targets the five clusters since these are more experienced and well versed with the effects

of greening practices such as green procurement practice at Uasin Gishu County. Stratified random sampling was used to obtain a sample of 111 from a target population of 1140 from Procurement, Finance, Human Resource, Operations and Stores departments. to find the final adjusted sample size, allowing a non-response rate of 10%, the adjusted sample size was $92+(92*0.1) = 111$. Suitable, usable and adequate data for the study was collected through administering questionnaires. The study adopted both quantitative and qualitative approaches, implying that both descriptive statistics and inferential statistics were employed. Quantitative data collected from the document analysis was analyzed statistically using the Statistical Package for Social Scientist (SPSS version 24). The study tested the significance level of each independent variable against the dependent variable at a 95% confidence level using ANOVA, Correlation and regression techniques. A 95% confidence interval reflects a significance level of 0.05. this shows that for an independent variable to have a significance effect on the dependent variable, the p- value should be below the significance level of 0.05. This regression model was used to test the relationship between the implementation of green procurement as a linear function of the independent variables.

Findings And Discussion

This section covers the research findings and discussion. A total of 92 respondents were selected for the study, with 96 questionnaires distributed to them with the 4 extra questionnaires distributed to 4 additional participants to cater for losses. From the 96 questionnaires distributed, 95 were filled and returned, meaning a response rate of 99%. The high response rates facilitated the adequacy of the data. This was in line with Orodho (2009) that a response rate above 50% contributes towards the gathering of sufficient data. The data is representative of generalized opinions' of respondents to the study problem in the target population.

Descriptive and Correlation Statistics

Supply chain performance was 3.88 (SD = 0.760), which shows that the majority of the employees agreed with the level of supply chain performance at the County government of Uasin Gishu.. The overall mean response was 3.55 (SD = 0.897), showing agreement on the existence of environment management support in the County government of Uasin Gishu. The overall mean was 2.701 (SD = 0.631) that showed that according to the majority of the employees of Uasin Gishu County, there is product re-usability practiced in by the County. The findings in Table 1 show that environment management support has a positive and significant relationship with supply chain performance , $\rho = 0.410$, $p < 0.01$, meaning that there is 0.410 probability that supply chain performance will increase with the increase in environment management support. Finally, product re-usability has a positive and significant relationship with supply chain performance , $\rho = 0.136$, $p < 0.05$, meaning that with an increase in product re-usability, there is a probability of 0.136 that supply chain performance will increase. The assessment of inter-factor correlations revealed a positive and significant relationship between the independent factors. These findings provide enough evidence to suggest that there was a linear relationship between internal environment management, investment recovery with supply chain performance.

Table 1. Descriptive and Correlation Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Supply chain performance	Environment management support	Product re-usability
Supply chain performance	3.880	0.760	1		
Environmental Management Support	3.545	0.897	0.410**	1	
Product Re-Usability	3.701	0.631	0.136*	0.406**	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Multiple Regression Results

This study sought to determine the effect of green supply chain adoption on supply chain performance in county governments in Kenya, a case of the Uasin Gishu County government. The results in Table 2 showed that all the four predictors (environment management, product reusability) explained a 50.6% variation of supply chain performance. This showed that considering the four study independent variables, there is a probability of predicting supply chain performance by 50.6% (R-squared =0.506). The findings in Table 2 indicated that the above discussed coefficient of determination was significant as evidence of F (4, 90) ratio of 147.606 with $p < 0.001$. Thus, the model was fit to predict supply chain performance using environment management, product reusability.

The findings in Table 2 show that environment management support has a positive and significant effect on supply chain performance, $\beta_3 = 0.505$, $p < 0.001$ such that with each unit increase in environment management support, supply chain performance will increase by 0.505 units. In line with these findings, Kumar and Chandrakar (2012) assert that top management support can affect new system initiatives success. Cross-functional efforts like supply chain performance are likely to benefit too. On the other hand, while focusing on the level and source of support, there is a risk that this is only a preserve of the top management and thus, organizational innovations may remain stuck at the initial idea stage (Perotti *et al.*, 2012). However, given its importance, it is not just top-level managers from whom support is needed; support from mid-level managers is also important to the successful implementation of environmental practices. Also, in line with the sustainability theory, Bolton (2006) defines sustainability for any individual, organization, or institution that is associated with a firm and is either affected by the firm in some way or affects the firm's action and goals. On the other hand, Theyel (2010) asserts that firms that seek to develop and implement a proactive strategic environmental commitment are considered to be more aware of stakeholder needs than those that are only concerned with meeting minimum environmental regulation requirements.

The findings in Table 2 show that product re-usability has a negative and significant effect on supply chain performance, $\beta_4 = -0.150$, $p < 0.001$ such that with each unit increase in product re-usability implementation by the County government, there will be 0.150 decreases in supply chain performance. These findings have an implication that seems to point towards the lack of a clear-cut understanding and implementation of product re-usability. Analyzing the potential consequences of usability is essential because the anticipated consequences of usability play an important role in the prioritization of usability (Hussein & Shalle, 2014). Given the findings of this study, product developers often describe usability as fuzzy and ungraspable (Shang *et al.*, 2010) such that in order to improve usability, you need a shared understanding of it (Roberts *et al.*, 2008). Defining usability is one approach, but creating shared understanding might not require establishing a formal, explicit definition (Liu *et al.*, 2012). Thus, there are benefits that can be accrued from product re-usability strategies, this is, however, pegged on the approach used.

Table 2: Multiple Regression Results

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	SE	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	2.596	0.138		18.847	0.000
Environment management support	0.309	0.032	0.505	9.814	0.000
Product re-usability	-0.060	0.017	-0.150	-3.530	0.000
R	0.712				
R-Square	0.506				
Adjusted R-Square	0.501				
Std. Error of the Estimate	0.241				
F	147.606				
Sig.	0.000				

a Dependent Variable: Supply chain performance

Conclusion and Recommendations

The main objective of the study was to determine the effect of green supply chain adoption on supply chain performance in county governments in Kenya, a case of Uasin Gishu County government. The findings have shown that environmental management support enhances supply chain performance. However, product re-usability has a negative effect on supply chain performance. There are also gaps identified in Green supply chain implementation in Uasin Gishu County that curtail supply chain performance. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are put forward: There is also a need to address the structuring and restructuring of teams that are responsible for environmental improvements and putting in place a total quality environmental management plan and implementing it. This also means putting in place an enabling environment that would foster idea exchange and implementation. Finally, since there is the sub-optimal implementation of product re-usability policies or the policies are not able to effectively address the existing gaps in product re-usability. Proper enforcement mechanisms for product re-usability would enhance its effect on supply chain performance. This main study objective is to assess the effect of Green supply chain performance on supply management performance. From the study findings, the findings were only limited to Green supply chain adoption. Thus, more research and studies should be carried out to determine other factors that affect supply chain performance. Some of the factors can be those in legal constraints and the spread of technology. This would enable the researchers and concerned investors to mitigate the effects of such factors and hence enhance supply chain performance. Furthermore, since the County government is a public entity, there is a need to further research on the private sector firms and organizations to have comparable findings in enhancing the knowledge of supply chain performance.

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